

Handcycling classification: a first look into the current classification system

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Abstract According to the International Paralympic Committee, classification must minimize the impact of impairment on performance through an evidence-based system. However, current handcycling classification is mostly based on expert opinion. The aim of this study was to explore whether average race speed is different between sport classes. Official time trial results of men's H1-H5 classes from the Union Cycliste Internationale's Championships Greenville 2014, Nottwil 2015 and Pietermaritzburg 2017 were used. Distances were 8.3km for H1 and 16.6km for H2-H5 in Greenville; 14km for H1-H2 and 15.5km for H3-H5 in Nottwil; and 15.5km for H1-H2 and 23.3km for H3-H5 in Pietermaritzburg. Average speed was calculated from race results. Kruskal-Wallis tests followed by Mann-Whitney U tests with Bonferroni correction were conducted to compare the average speed of the top 10 athletes between consecutive classes on each separate championship. Under a significance threshold set at .0125, there were significant differences between H1-H2 ($p=.002$ in Greenville; and $p<.001$ in Nottwil and Pietermaritzburg) and H2-H3 ($p<.001$ in Greenville and Pietermaritzburg; and $p=.009$ in Nottwil). There were no significant differences between H3-H4 ($p=.089$ in Greenville; $p=.052$ in Nottwil; and $p=.143$ in Pietermaritzburg) and H4-H5 ($p=.123$ in Greenville; $p=.604$ in Nottwil; $p=.968$ in Pietermaritzburg). Differences in median speed were less than 2 km/h in all events between H3-H4 and H4-H5, having H4 and H5 the same median speed in Pietermaritzburg (34.9 km/h). Hence, the consecutive classes H3-H4 and H4-H5 showed comparable race speed in all championships. The potential confounding of different variables (e.g. inclination, race distance, handbike type) does not allow us to make strong assumptions only based on speed as a performance measure. However, our results stress the need for a stronger research into the current handcycling classification system.

Keywords Handcycling, classification, time trial, speed, velocity

Introduction

Handcycling is a popular sport among people with physical impairments (Hettinga et al. 2010), which has been part of the Paralympic games since 2004 (IPC, 2018). As part of the Paralympic movement, handcycling must comply with a specific code developed by the International Paralympic Committee (IPC). An important pillar of the development of Paralympic sports consists on the creation of a classification system that aims to promote sport participation among athletes with disabilities by minimizing the impact of their impairment on the sport competition (Tweedy and Vanlandewijck, 2011). The current handcycling classification system has been applied since 2014

when the sport changed from 4 to 5 sport classes (Union Cycliste International, 2018). To be compliant with the IPC's code the classification system must be evidence-based, however, several sports including handcycling are mostly based on expert opinion (Tweedy et al. 2016). There is no scientific evidence on the relationship between the current handcycling classification system and the performance outcome. Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore whether average speed is different between the 5 handcycling sport classes. We hypothesized that a valid classification system would lead to an average race velocity that is significantly different between sport classes.

Methods

Time trials results were collected from the Union Cycliste International website (<https://www.uci.org/para-cycling/results>) and used to analyze handcycling performance during competition. To avoid a large heterogeneity among athlete's training level we only used the world championships time trial results of the top ten male athletes of each class. The world championship is one of the most important yearly event for elite athletes, and therefore only highly trained athletes participate. Data was collected from the world championships in Greenville (2014), Nottwil (2015) and Pietermaritzburg (2017). Information regarding the time trials results and different distances can be seen in Table 1. Average speed was calculated by converting the race time of the time trial of each athlete to average velocity in km/h. Kuskal-wallis test was conducted to investigate whether there was a difference in groups for each separate championship, followed by a Mann-Whitney U test with Bonferroni correction for each of the consecutive sport classes comparison. The adjusted significance threshold was set at $p < 0.0125$.

Results

Table 1. World championships since 2014

World Championship		H1	H2	H3	H4	H5
Greenville 2014	Distance (km)	8.3	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Sample size (n)	4	10	10	10	10
	Mdn average velocity (km/h)	21.4	29.6	36.8	37.9	36.7
	Interquartile range (km)	1.3	4.8	2.4	1.8	3.2
Nottwil 2015	Distance (km)	14	14	15.5	15.5	15.5
	Sample size (n)	10	10	10	10	9
	Mdn average velocity (km/h)	17.6	26.4	28.8	29.8	31.3
	Interquartile range (km)	2.4	3.1	1.9	1.9	2.5
Pietermaritzburg 2017	Distance (km)	15.5	15.5	23.3	23.3	23.3
	Sample size (n)	8	8	10	10	9
	Mdn average velocity (km/h)	18.1	26.4	34.1	34.9	34.9
	Interquartile range (km)	2.6	6.4	1.7	2.4	3.2

Table 1 shows the different world championships analyzed and the respective race distance, median average velocity, interquartile range and sample size for each sport class. Up to the time of data collection, only 3 championships were organized since 2014 when the classification system

was changed to five classes. Participation of international elite athletes in some sport classes was limited, and therefore we were not able to have results of the top 10 athletes from each group.

There were significant differences in average speed in all events between the consecutive classes H1-H2 ($U=0$, $Z=-2.82$, $p=.002$, $r=-.76$ in Greenville; $U=0$, $Z=-3.78$, $p<.001$, $r=-.85$ in Nottwil; $U=0$, $Z=-3.361$, $p<.001$, $r=-.84$ in Pietermaritzburg), and H2-H3 ($U=0$, $Z=-3.78$, $p<.001$, $r=-.85$ in Greenville; $U=16$, $Z=-2.57$, $p=.009$, $r=-.57$ in Nottwil; $U=0$, $Z=-3.554$, $p<.001$, $r=-.84$ in Pietermaritzburg). However, there were no significant differences between the classes H3-H4 ($U=27$, $Z=-1.739$, $p=.089$, $r=-.29$ in Greenville; $U=24$, $Z=-1.965$, $p=.052$, $r=-0.44$ in Nottwil; $U=30$, $Z=-1.512$, $p=0.143$, $r=-0.34$ in Pietermaritzburg) and H4-H5 ($U=29.5$, $Z=-1.55$, $p=.123$, $r=-.35$ in Greenville; $U=38$, $Z=-.572$, $p=.604$, $r=-.13$ in Nottwil; $U=44$, $Z=-.082$, $p=.968$, $r=-.02$ in Pietermaritzburg). The largest difference in median speed was found between H1-H2 in Nottwil, with H2 being 8.8km/h faster than H1. Contrariwise, differences in median speed were less than 2 km/h in all events between H3-H4 and H4-H5, showing the same median speed for H4 and H5 in Pietermaritzburg (34.9 km/h).

Conclusion and discussion

Based on our results, the consecutive classes H3-H4 and H4-H5 showed comparable average race speeds in all championships, while H1-H2 and H2-H3 showed significant differences in all events. Average speed is associated with the distance of a race and, therefore, the different distances observed may limit our analysis of H1-H2 and H2-H3. Additionally, H5 athletes compete in a kneeling position (arm-trunk powered) instead of the recumbent position used by athletes from H1 to H4 (arm-powered). It is known that these 2 different handbike settings influence power production (Kouwijzer et al. 2018) and, consequently, the average speed achieved. These confounding variables together with the sample size does not allow us to make strong assumptions only based on average speed as a performance measure. However, stronger assumptions can be made regarding differences between H3-H4. Both classes did not show significant differences besides competing with the same type of handbike and the same distance in each event. Therefore, our results stress the need for profounder research into the current handcycling classification.

References

- Hettinga FJ, Valent L, Groen W, van Drongelen S, de Groot S, van der Woude LHV. (2010) Hand-Cycling: An Active Form of Wheeled Mobility, Recreation, and Sports. *Phys Med Rehabil Clin N Am.*; 21(1):127–40.
- IPC Sport Data Management System. Data Source, International Paralympic Committee. 2018. Available from: <https://www.paralympic.org/sdms/hira/web>
- Tweedy SM, Vanlandewijck YC. (2011) International Paralympic Committee position standbackground and scientific principles of classification in Paralympic sport. *Br J Sports Med.*;45(4):259–69.
- Tweedy SM, Mann D, Vanlandewijck YC. (2016) Research needs for the development of evidence-based systems of classification for physical, vision, and intellectual impairments. In: Vanlandewijck YC, Thompson WR, editors. *Training and Coaching the Paralympic Athlete*. First Edit. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.; p. 122–49.
- Kouwijzer I, Nooijen CFJ, van Breukelen K, Janssen TW, de Groot S. (2018). Effects of push-off ability and handcycle type on handcycling performance in able-bodied participants. *J Rehabil Med*; 50: 87-92